

Influence of system pressure on gas–solid reactions for thermochemical energy storage in a suspension reactor

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ABSTRACT

Thermochemical energy storage using salt hydrates is a promising approach to store medium to low-temperature heat, but previously investigated reactor designs often suffer from poor heat and mass transfer, inhomogeneous moisture distribution or particle agglomeration. This study examines the effect of system pressure on suitable solid–gas reactions in a novel three-phase suspension reactor that aims to solve these problems. The reversible dehydration reactions of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, H_3BO_3 , $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were investigated under vacuum (≥ 50 mbar) and pressurised conditions (≤ 8 bar) using liquid water for hydration. Dehydration onset temperatures were reduced by 33–66 °C (e.g., $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: 105 °C \rightarrow 57 °C), with dehydration rates increasing up to 2.1 times compared to ambient pressure. All four materials demonstrated stable performance over five charging–discharging cycles without particle agglomeration. Hydration experiments for K_2CO_3 and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at up to 8 bar showed mostly pressure-independent reaction rates, with $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ exhibiting increased temperature lift at higher suspension temperatures. These findings demonstrate that system pressure control in suspension reactors can significantly reduce charging temperatures and charging time, and improve operational flexibility of the technology, supporting its scale-up for seasonal or industrial heat storage applications.

1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation for research into low-temperature heat storage

Limiting global warming to 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels requires a significant reduction of greenhouse gas emissions [1], especially by improving energy efficiency and expanding the use of renewable heat sources [2]. A major untapped opportunity lies in the recovery of industrial waste heat, which currently accounts for over half (52 %) of global industrial energy consumption. Most of this is low-temperature heat (≤ 100 °C), making up nearly 77 % (107.74 PJ), with another 14 % (19.25 PJ) at medium temperatures (100–299 °C) [3]. Due to its low Carnot potential, low-temperature heat is best stored and reused directly rather than converted into electricity. At the same time, the residential sector, which uses 78 % of its energy for heating and cooling, with 57 % still reliant on fossil fuels, presents a clear demand for such recovered heat [4]. The effective use of waste heat in this way is constrained by spatial and temporal mismatches between supply and demand. The use of thermal energy storage (TES) technologies could be the answer to bridging these gaps, which would allow for further decarbonisation of

heating and cooling.

1.2. Thermochemical energy storage using salt hydrates

Thermal energy storage. TES technologies can be divided into three categories according to their working principle: sensible heat storage (SHS) and latent heat storage (LHS), and thermochemical energy storage (TCES) [5]. SHS stores sensible heat, usually in a solid or liquid storage medium like water, oil, rock pebbles and cement [6,7] and is highly established for short-term heat storage [8,9]. LHS ensures higher storage densities by utilising endo- and exothermic phase changes of so-called phase change materials (PCM) like paraffins, fatty acids, salt hydrates and metals [5]. While primarily suited for short- to medium-term storage, subcooling can extend the storage duration [10,11]. The third method, TCES, offers the highest energy density as it stores heat in either a sorption process or a reversible chemical reaction [11]. Heat is introduced to component A, as shown in Equation (1), which undergoes an endothermic reaction to form components B and C, which are then stored separately. When the heat is needed again, components B and C are recombined to form component A and release the heat in an

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Nomenclature			
Symbols		X_i	conversion rate. –
$c_{p,i}$	specific heat capacity of component i. kJ/(kgK)	x,y	variables for linear regression. –
$\Delta_R H$	reaction enthalpy. J/mol	ν	stoichiometric factor. –
ΔH°	enthalpy at standard conditions. J/mol	w_i	mass fraction or content of component i. wt%
K	equilibrium constant. –	ρ_i	density of component i. kg/m ³
m_i	mass of component i. kg	Subscripts	
p	pressure. bar	(g), (l), (s)	gaseous, liquid, solid phase
p^+	reference pressure = 1 bar. bar	Abbreviations	
p_{H_2O}	partial pressure of water. bar	CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
r_i	dehydration reaction rate. s ⁻¹	DSC	differential scanning calorimetry
R	ideal gas constant. J/(molK)	EEA	European Environment Agency
R^2	coefficient of determination. –	LHS	latent heat storage
$\Delta_R S^\circ$	entropy at standard conditions. J/(molK)	PCM	phase change material
$T, \Delta T$	temperature, temperature difference. K or °C	SHS	sorption heat storage
t	time. s	TCES	thermochemical energy storage
$V(H_2O)$	volume of water. ml	TCM	thermochemical material
V_i	volume of component i. m ³	TGA	thermogravimetric analysis

exothermic reaction.

Separating the components during storage prevents self-discharge of the system, enabling long-term storage without insulation [12,13]. Due to this, TCES is particularly suited for seasonal storage and is the focus of this study.

Water-based thermochemical materials. Thermochemical materials (TCMs) used for TCES in the low- to medium temperature range include sorption materials like zeolites and silica gels, metal hydrides and metal oxides, ammonia-based TCMs and water-based TCMs such as salt hydrates [12,14,15]. Especially water-based TCM continue to be widely researched due to the non-toxicity, low environmental impact and high availability of water [16]. In addition, salt hydrates themselves are non-combustible, mostly non-toxic, biodegradable and recyclable as well as economically viable as they are available in abundance [17]. This, combined with their relatively high energy density [15] in the investigated temperature range (≤ 165 °C), is the reason they are chosen for this work.

Table 1 shows the reaction systems investigated in this work and their reaction temperature during dehydration and hydration as found in previous works [18,19,20]. The values were obtained in thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) at fixed water vapour pressures p_{H_2O} , for the salt hydrates calcium chloride dihydrate ($\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), copper sulphate pentahydrate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and potassium carbonate sesquihydrate ($\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) [18] or under an argon atmosphere for boric acid (H_3BO_3) [19].

Influence of pressure on the equilibrium temperature. The measured reaction temperatures for the dehydration and hydration reactions in Table 1 correspond to the low water vapour pressures applied during the

TGA. As previous works state, knowing the reaction or rather the equilibrium temperature of the (de)hydration at the applied water vapour pressure, is essential to assess its suitability for any thermal application [21]. The dependence of the reaction equilibrium on water vapour pressure and temperature can be described by the Van't Hoff equation, which will be discussed in the following Chapter 2.4 [22]. In general, the dehydration reaction is expected to be favoured by low water vapour pressure and high temperature, due to the endothermic nature of the reaction and the associated volume increase from water vapour formation, as explained by Le Chatelier's principle [23]. In contrast, the exothermic hydration reaction is largely insensitive to pressure and favoured by lower temperatures, although higher temperatures could also increase the reaction rate according to collision theory [24].

1.3. Reactor concept

TCES reactor concepts. Most TCES systems in the relevant temperature range of 50–250 °C have so far only been tested at laboratory scale [12]. Published reviews about this topic discuss three main reactor concepts: fixed/packed bed, moving bed, and fluidised bed reactor [11,25,26,27]. Each concept has benefits and limitations, especially regarding heat and mass transfer, particle handling and the complexity of the system. A summary is shown in Table 2.

One of the main problems that research into water-based TCES materials aims to solve is the agglomeration of particles [25,29]. Researchers use modified reactor types like vibrating moving bed reactors [30] or bubbling fluidised bed reactors [31] but still need to introduce additional host materials to avoid the agglomeration of the hygroscopic particles. Host materials include (alumino)silicates, expanded graphite or foams [25,32,33,34,35,36,37] or solid adsorbents like zeolites,

Table 1
Reaction temperatures and energy densities of the TCMs from literature [18,19,20].

Reaction equation	$T_{\text{dehydration,min}}$ ($p_{H_2O} = 20$ mbar)	$T_{\text{hydration,max}}$ ($p_{H_2O} = 12$ mbar)	Energy density
	°C	°C	GJ/m ³
$\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)} \leftrightarrow \text{CaCl}_2_{(s)} + 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$	112	63	1.464
$\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3_{(s)} \leftrightarrow \text{HBO}_2_{(s)}^* + \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$	137**	n.a.	1.476
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)} \leftrightarrow \text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)} + 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$	40	30	2.073
$\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)} \leftrightarrow \text{K}_2\text{CO}_3_{(s)} + 1.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$	65	59	1.220

*orthorhombic crystal modification of metaboric acid HBO_2 .

**under argon atmosphere, $p_{H_2O} = 0$ mbar.

Table 2
Comparison of reactor designs used for TCES [11,25,26,27,28].

Reactor type	Advantages	Disadvantages
Fixed bed reactor (Packed bed or honeycomb structure)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple design • Good solid–gas contact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High pressure drop (packed bed) • Uneven reaction, overhydration and hot spots (packed bed) • Low volumetric energy density (honeycomb)
Moving bed reactor (Gravity-driven or vibrated)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple design • Good solid–gas contact • Vibration reduces agglomeration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inhomogeneous solid flow and clumping (gravity-driven) • Complex and high energy consumption (vibrated)
Fluidised bed reactor (Bubbling, agitated or circulating)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good heat and mass transfer • Homogeneous temperature and moisture distribution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High pressure drop (bubbling) • High energy consumption (agitated) • Particle attrition • Erosion • Complex fluid dynamics
Suspension reactor (Stirred tank)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good heat and mass transfer • Homogeneous temperature and moisture distribution • Oil prevents agglomeration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High energy consumption (stirrer) • Complex fluid dynamics • Less studied in the TCES context

metal–organic frameworks and silica gel. These host matrices enhance the structural stability but typically reduce the volumetric energy storage density of the system [32,38,39,40]. Still, some composite materials using $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been reported to reach energy storage densities of 1.4 GJ/m^3 [29] and 0.96 GJ/m^3 [41] respectively. While showing promising results these materials have so far only been tested in thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and need to be investigated in a reactor prototype.

The second main research focus in the field of TCES is an optimal reactor system that ensures efficient heat and mass transfer [42], as the reactor design significantly influences the efficiency of the heat storage cycle [15]. Fluidised bed reactors offer improved heat and mass transfer, but again, host matrices are needed for salt hydrates, as the pure materials agglomerate in this type of reactor [43]. Recent research using higher temperature water-based TCES materials also suggests the use of metal foams and fins and gradient porosity inside the fixed bed reactor to improve heat and mass transfer [44,45].

The suspension reactor. As mentioned in Table 2, another new option in the field of TCES, which is used in this work, is a three-phase suspension reactor that uses an inert liquid to suspend the solid particles. This type of reactor, particularly in the form of a stirred tank, can achieve a homogeneous distribution of solids in the liquid phase and maintain uniform temperature distribution [28]. Like fluidised bed reactors, they typically improve heat and mass transfer, but the suspension medium and the stirrer also avoid agglomeration without introducing a host matrix. The suspension method for TCES using salt hydrates and the reactor concept have already been introduced in previous works,

Table 3
Used materials and oils [51,52,53,54].

Raw material	CAS	Producer	Purity	$c_{p,i}$ (25 °C)	ρ_i (25 °C)
–	–	–	%	kJ/(kgK)	kg/m ³
Calcium chloride dihydrate	10035–04-8	Diaclean	≥99	1.17	1830
Orthoboric acid	10043–35-3	Carl Roth	≥99.8	1.32	1440
Copper sulphate pentahydrate	7758–99-8	Carl Roth	≥98	1.13	2286
Potassium carbonate	584–08-7	Diaclean	≥99	0.83	2043 (sesqui)
Mineral oil (Q-32-N)	64742–54-7	Fragol	–	1.99	868
Silicone oil (X-400-A)	Mixture	Fragol	–	1.53	960

including a theoretical kinetics analysis [46], batch experiments [47] and experiments in a lab-scale reactor in continuous operation mode [48].

Another distinction of this approach is the use of liquid water for the discharging (hydration) step, rather than gaseous water as in other works published in this field [32,38,42,49,50] and more. This choice is driven by practical considerations as the handling of liquid water is simpler than managing water vapour or moist air due to the difference in volume and the fact that gas bubbles may have shorter contact times with the salt particles compared to liquid droplets, potentially limiting reaction efficiency. Additionally, in the context of seasonal thermal energy storage, it could be beneficial to use liquid water as it is more readily available than water vapour and needs no additional heat to be evaporated.

1.4. Aim of the research

As described in Chapter 1.2, the equilibrium temperature of the (de)hydration reaction at a given water vapour pressure determines the temperature level at which heat can be stored using a solid–gas thermochemical system. This study investigates how lowering the system pressure in a suspension reactor affects the onset temperature and reaction rate of the charging reaction (dehydration) of the selected TCM: $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, H_3BO_3 , $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

In addition, the feasibility of discharging (hydration) using liquid water at elevated temperatures and pressures is examined by comparing the temperature rise and reaction time at different pressures and temperatures. These tests are conducted in small-scale batch setups as a basis for future scale-up. Understanding the interactions between pressure, temperature and reaction rate is crucial for developing a continuous process with stable charging and discharging conditions.

This work addresses a current gap in the literature by providing experimental data on the pressure-dependent behaviour of salt hydrate reactions in a three-phase suspension reactor. This type of reactor has not yet been fully studied in the context of TCES, but it could offer advantages in terms of heat transfer and material handling compared to other types of reactors.

2. Method and materials

2.1. Materials

Table 3 shows the producers of the used TCM and the inert suspension media, mineral and silicone oil, as well as their Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS) number, purity, specific heat capacity $c_{p,i}$ and density ρ_i . The hydrated chemicals are usually more affordable, except for potassium carbonate, so the anhydrous form (K_2CO_3) was used instead.

2.2. Energy storage density in oil

Energy storage densities are a key factor when choosing a TCM, as it will determine the required size of the reactor and storage tanks to store a certain amount of heat. The potential energy storage densities of the TCM investigated in this work are calculated using the theoretical reaction enthalpies and the suspension density $\rho_{\text{suspension}}$. This suspension

Fig. 1. Experimental setups for dehydration at lower pressure in a three-necked flask (a) and hydration at higher pressure in a steel unit (b).

Table 4
Physical properties of the low-pressure and high-pressure setups.

setup	low-pressure setup(s)	high-pressure setup
flask/reactor volume	500 ml (flask)/800 ml (reactor)	450 ml
suspension volume	~200 ml	~200 ml
salt fraction	10–30 wt% salt	40 wt% salt
stirrer type	stirring paddle/	pitched blade impeller
stirrer speed	300 rpm	1000 rpm
heating	oil bath (flask)/heating mantle (reactor)	electric heating mantle
thermocouple	type K (± 2.2 °C or ± 0.75 %)	type K (± 2.2 °C or ± 0.75 %)
system pressure range	50–1013 mbar (absolute)	0–8 bar (relative)
pressure control	vacuum pump (accuracy ± 2 mbar) + control pressure gauge (accuracy ± 4 %)	nitrogen tank + pressure gauge (accuracy ± 0.5 %)

density is calculated using Equation (2), the densities of the salt hydrate ρ_{solid} , the oil ρ_{oil} and the solid content w_{solid} .

$$\rho_{suspension} = \frac{1}{\frac{w_{solid}}{\rho_{solid}} + \frac{1-w_{solid}}{\rho_{oil}}} \quad (2)$$

The exact procedure is described in more detail in previous work on $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by Schmieder et al. [47].

2.3. Experimental setups and procedures

As explained in the introduction, this work investigates the dehydration and hydration of the TCMs in a lab-scale suspension reactor. The two setups shown in Fig. 1 are a three-necked flask setup (low-pressure setup) with an attached vacuum pump to investigate the dehydration at pressures down to 50 mbar (Fig. 1 (a)) and a steel reactor (high-pressure setup) with an attached nitrogen pump to apply pressure to the hydration reaction of up to 8 bar relative (Fig. 1 (b)). To investigate cycle stability over several runs at 50 mbar, a modified version of the low-pressure setup is used: the flask is replaced with a batch glass reactor that is heated by a controlled heating mantle instead of the oil bath. This setup is otherwise identical to the one shown in Fig. 1 (a) and is

described in more detail in Schmieder et al. 2025 [47]. Table 4 gives an overview of the most important properties of the two setups.

Dehydration starting temperature at lower pressures: Fig. 1 (a). The dehydration of the reaction systems is conducted in a three-necked flask within a service oil bath, which provides insight into the reaction zone during system pressure variations. The 500 ml flask is filled with 200 ml of suspension and is heated by the oil bath on a heating plate, with manual temperature regulation and a thermocouple (type K) measuring the suspension temperature. A membrane vacuum pump attached to the cooler outlet lowers the system pressure, while a pressure gauge measures pressure inside the reaction zone. The pressure is set to a constant value (50–1013 mbar) at the self-regulating pump, and the suspension is heated slowly (0.17–0.19 K/min) until bubble formation is visible. The starting temperature is noted as the suspension temperature at which the bubble formation first starts at the set pressure. This value is assumed to be close to the reaction equilibrium. A more detailed setup and component description are provided in Table 4 and previous work by Schmieder et al. 2025 [47] (called Setup 2).

Dehydration (50 mbar)-hydration (1013 mbar) cycles. The mentioned batch glass reactor used to conduct the dehydration-hydration cycles is similar to the setup shown in Fig. 1 (a), but has

Table 5
Heating rates for dehydration at 50 mbar for the five cycles.

$\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$		H_3BO_3		$\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$		$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$		
T	rate	T	rate	T	rate	T	rate	
°C	K/min	°C	K/min	°C	K/min	°C	K/min	
100	5	110	5	100	5	70	5	
145	0.25	120	0.5	140	0.5	90	0.5*	*+ hold for 100 min
165	0.5	130	0.05	140	0	100	0.5°	°+ hold for 80 min
$t_{\text{total}} = 235$ min		$t_{\text{total}} = 237$ min		$t_{\text{total}} = 120$ min		$t_{\text{total}} = 249$ min		

automatically controlled heating, and the amount of condensed water is tracked using the burette. The reactor is filled with 250 g of suspension consisting of 30 wt% solid material, 70 wt% mineral oil (for $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, H_3BO_3 and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) or mineral oil with 23 wt% silicone oil (for $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$). The heating rate and total running time t_{total} , for the dehydration at 50 mbar for the different TCMs are shown in Table 5. All heating profiles are designed to slow down heating once the reaction speeds up to avoid excessive foaming. The heating rates for $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ can be chosen higher than for the other systems, as it is used in silicone oil, which decreases foaming due to its lower interfacial tension with water (34.4 mN/m compared to 49.0 mN/m for mineral oil). $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires a particularly slow heating rate as the high water content causes excessive foaming at 50 mbar.

The conversion of the dehydration X_i , which can be tracked over time is calculated by dividing the volume of the water collected $V_{\text{condensed}}$ by the stoichiometric amount of water in the solid phase $V_{\text{stoichiometric}}$ as shown in Equation (3):

$$X_i = \frac{V_{\text{condensed}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})}{V_{\text{stoichiometric}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})} \quad (3)$$

For $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, comparisons of the dehydration reaction rate r_i at lower pressure (50 mbar) and ambient pressure (1013 mbar) at the same temperature are conducted. The dehydration reaction rate r_i (unit s^{-1}) is determined by calculating the derivative of the conversion X_i according to Equation (4) and the maximum reaction rates mentioned in the results section refer to the peaks of the resulting $\frac{dX_i}{dt}$ curves.

$$r_i = \frac{dX_i}{dt} \quad (4)$$

After dehydration, the suspension is cooled down to room temperature and the hydration is performed by adding liquid water through a syringe. The temperature rise in the suspension is measured using a thermocouple (type K). After that, the next dehydration-hydration cycle is started to perform five full cycles. The exact setup and procedure are again described in more detail as ‘‘Setup 1a’’ in Schmieder et al. 2025 [47].

Hydration at higher pressures: Fig. 1 (b): This setup consists of a high-pressure steel reactor designed by Parr Instrument Company with a high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) water pump attached. The physical properties are given in Table 4. The reactor has a nitrogen tank attached that can apply relative pressure of up to 10 bars and is therefore sufficient for the hydration experiments, which were performed at 0, 4 and 8 bar relative system pressure. The pressure inside the reactor is measured by a pressure gauge and the nitrogen bottle is used to apply pressure until the desired value is reached after which the valve is closed. The temperature reading is only available in whole numbers, as the reactor was originally designed for different experiments at higher temperatures and pressures. The experiments were conducted using a

suspension consisting of 40 wt% $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 60 wt% silicone oil or mineral oil respectively. To conduct the experiment the reaction vessel is filled with 180 g of suspension, sealed and pressurised with nitrogen to reach the desired relative pressure p_{relative} . The suspension is stirred at 1000 rpm and heated to the desired starting temperature T_0 . Once these parameters are set the stoichiometric amount of water is directed to the vessel at a flow rate of 10 ml/min. The water temperature is measured in the glass water tank, and the temperature and pressure in the vessel are tracked using SpecView. The maximum temperature rise ΔT and the time until this maximum is reached $t(T_{\text{max}})$ is recorded to see a change in behaviour at varied p_{relative} and T_0 .

2.4. Equilibrium curves of the dehydration at lower pressures

The aforementioned Van't Hoff equation defines the equilibrium constant K . A widely used linearised form using reaction enthalpy $\Delta_R H^\circ$ and entropy $\Delta_R S^\circ$ at standard conditions is given in Equation (5) [55]:

$$\ln K = -\frac{\Delta_R H^\circ}{RT} + \frac{\Delta_R S^\circ}{R} \quad (5)$$

R is the universal gas constant and T is the temperature in K. The equation can be modified by approximating K by $\frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{p^+}$ to describe the equilibrium of a solid–gas reaction. The reactions at hand involve a solid TCM and gaseous water. p^+ in the equation presents the reference pressure (1 bar) and $p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ the water vapour partial pressure. Additionally, ν describes the stoichiometric factor of the respective reaction [22] The resulting equation is given in Equation (6):

$$\ln\left(\frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{p^+}\right) = -\frac{\Delta_R H^\circ}{R\nu} \frac{1}{T} + \frac{\Delta_R S^\circ}{R\nu} = -a \cdot \frac{1}{T} + b \quad (6)$$

The equation predicts how the equilibrium temperature of the reaction changes when different water vapour partial pressures are applied. In the suspension reactor with an inert liquid suspension medium, the system pressure is assumed to be equal to the water vapour partial pressure $p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ since the suspended particles are surrounded by water vapour only. Therefore, changing the system pressure to lower values should decrease the starting temperature of the dehydration reaction in the suspension. The values for the dehydration starting temperature at different system pressures which are obtained in the three-necked flask setup can be used to draw the Van't Hoff plots ($\ln\left(\frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{p^+}\right)$ vs. T^{-1} in $1000 \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$) for the investigated systems. Additionally, equilibrium curves ($p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ vs. T in $^\circ\text{C}$) are given in the results section. The linear Equation (6) is used to calculate the standard enthalpies $\Delta_R H^\circ$ and entropies $\Delta_R S^\circ$ of the dehydration reaction by defining a and b as seen in Equation (7) and (8):

Table 6
Energy storage density of the different TCM in oil; orthorhombic crystal modification of metaboric acid HBO_2 [20,51].

		salt/suspension density	energy density $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(l)}$	energy density $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$
		kg/m ³	GJ/m ³	GJ/m ³
$\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)} \leftrightarrow \text{CaCl}_{2(s)} + 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$	solid density	1830	0.368	1.464
	bulk density	835	0.168	0.668
	30 wt% oil	1373	0.193	0.769
$\text{H}_3\text{BO}_{3(s)} \leftrightarrow \text{HBO}_{2(s)}^* + \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$	solid density	1440	0.452	1.476
	bulk density	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	30 wt% oil	1202	0.264	0.863
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)} \leftrightarrow \text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)} + 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$	solid density	2286	0.461	2.073
	bulk density	936	0.242	1.088
	30 wt% oil	1534	0.217	0.974
$\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)} \leftrightarrow \text{K}_2\text{CO}_{3(s)} + 1.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$	solid density	2043	0.404	1.220
	bulk density	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	30 wt% oil	1453	0.201	0.608

*orthorhombic crystal modification of metaboric acid HBO_2 .

$$\Delta_R H^\circ = a \cdot Rv \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta_R S^\circ = b \cdot Rv \quad (8)$$

2.5. Temperature correction during hydration at higher pressures

As it is not feasible to preheat the water added to the reactor, the water temperature T_w is much lower (17–20 °C) than the suspension starting temperature T_0 , which is varied between 25, 50 and 75 °C. Therefore, to compare the data, the measured temperature rise must be corrected to compensate for the temperature drop caused by the addition of cold water. Therefore, a mixing temperature T_{mix} between T_w and T_0 is calculated in Equation (9) in which i stands for w and 0 :

$$T_{mix} = \frac{\sum c_{p,i} \cdot m_i \cdot T_i}{\sum c_{p,i} \cdot m_i} \quad (9)$$

The specific heat $c_{p,i}$ of the solid material, oil and water are taken from Table 3. The mass values m_i are according to the suspension composition of 72 g K_2CO_3 , 25 g silicone oil and 83 g mineral oil and the stoichiometric water amount of 14 g. Equations (10) and (11) are then used to calculate the measured temperature rise $\Delta T_{measured}$ and the corrected temperature rise $\Delta T_{corrected}$ respectively.

$$\Delta T_{measured} = T_{max} - T_0 \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta T_{corrected} = T_{max} - T_{mix} \quad (11)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Energy density in oil

Table 6 shows the calculated theoretical energy storage densities, based on the measured solid and bulk densities of the TCM as well as a mixture of the TCM and 30 wt% mineral oil.

Like introducing a host matrix, the oil content decreases the volumetric energy density of the system compared to the solid density of the salt by decreasing the overall density of the suspension and the concentration of the reactive material. To keep the oil content low in the

storage tank, the scaled-up suspension reactor introduces a separation unit that reduces the oil content to 30 wt% oil [48]. Table 6 shows that the energy storage density using a suspension with 30 wt% oil can ensure similar volumetric energy densities to the available bulk densities of the salt hydrates $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$. At least for the $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and $K_2CO_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ systems, the energy storage densities are below those achieved in previously mentioned most promising works using composite materials [29,41].

3.2. Dehydration starting temperature at lower pressures

The equilibrium curves of the first dehydration step of the different TCMs are shown in Fig. 2 and are compared to other data from the literature. The literature values for enthalpy $\Delta_R H^\circ$ and entropy $\Delta_R S^\circ$ were used to reproduce these equilibrium curves according to Equation (6).

$CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$: Fig. 2 (a) shows the first dehydration step of $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ to $CaCl_2 \cdot H_2O$, which aligns closely with the equilibrium curve measured by Molenda et al. [50] in a fixed-bed reactor setup, while the hot-wire manometer measurements performed by Lannung [56] fit less closely. These results show that the measurement technique can have an impact on the obtained equilibrium lines. Overall, the starting temperature of the bubble formation decreases from 176 °C at ambient pressure to 109 °C at 50 mbar.

H_3BO_3 : For the reaction of H_3BO_3 to HBO_2 , seen in Fig. 2 (b), the comparison to literature is not trivial as three crystal modifications of the metaboric acid HBO_2 exist (orthorhombic α -(BOH) $_3O_3$, monoclinic β -(BOH) $_3O_3$ and cubic γ -(BOH) $_3O_3$) [57]. Depending on the crystal modification of HBO_2 formed the reaction enthalpy $\Delta_R H^\circ$ and entropy $\Delta_R S^\circ$ will be different. Density measurements of the dehydrated material suggest that the orthorhombic form is prevalent in the suspension. Fig. 2 (b) shows that the comparison graph created from the NBS tables [52] data for α -(BOH) $_3O_3$ fits the experimental data better than the one from HSC chemistry [51] for γ -(BOH) $_3O_3$, but there is still a difference in the slope below 400 mbar, so a distinct specification of the crystal modification is not possible. The starting temperature of the bubble formation decreases from 148 °C at ambient pressure to 116 °C at 50 mbar.

$CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$: The equilibrium curve of the dehydration of

Fig. 2. Equilibrium curves of the dehydration of $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ to $CaCl_2 \cdot H_2O$ (a), H_3BO_3 to HBO_2 (b), $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ to $CuSO_4 \cdot H_2O$ (c) and $K_2CO_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ to K_2CO_3 (d) and comparison with literature [50,51,52,56].

Fig. 3. Comparison of the experimental Van't Hoff plots of different reaction systems.

$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, shown in Fig. 2 (c), has the same slope as the comparison data from NBS tables [52] and HSC chemistry [51] with a systematic offset that could be caused by a different heating rate than the reference measurements, but is also within the measurement accuracy of the temperature elements of ± 4.5 °C. The measured starting temperature is most likely influenced by the presence of oil, which changes the mass transport conditions of the water vapour to the surface. The starting temperature of the bubble formation decreases from 105 °C (ambient pressure) to 57 °C (50 mbar).

K_2CO_3 : Fig. 2 (d) shows the experimental equilibrium curve of the dehydration of $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to K_2CO_3 , which is more comparable to the one from HSC chemistry [51] than from the NBS tables [52], which could again be caused by different heating rates or measurement inaccuracies in these measurements. The starting temperature of the bubble formation decreases from 147 °C at ambient pressure to 113 °C at 50 mbar.

The combined linearised Van't Hoff plots of the four systems are shown in Fig. 3, showing that the starting temperatures of the dehydration reactions of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have a higher pressure dependency than those of H_3BO_3 and $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. H_3BO_3 and $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ also have quite similar reaction temperatures. The trend line formulas for the linearised Van't Hoff plots are given in Fig. 3. The coefficients of determination R^2 are high at 0.98 for $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and

0.99 for the other systems, which fit the expected curves.

Therefore, the variables from the trend line formulas (a and b) are used to calculate enthalpy $\Delta_R H^\circ$ and entropy $\Delta_R S^\circ$ values of the reactions according to Equations (6), (7) and (8). Table 7 gives an overview of the resulting standard enthalpy $\Delta_R H^\circ$ and entropy $\Delta_R S^\circ$ values compared to the ones obtained from literature.

The values for $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ align closely with the comparison values, exhibiting a deviation lower than -10 %. The data for H_3BO_3 diverges significantly from the values obtained using either crystal modification of HBO_2 (-34 % to the orthorhombic form). This could be a result of the crystal modification changing at different temperatures. After the measurement, the orthorhombic form is present as determined by a density measurement. Furthermore, when comparing the resulting Van't Hoff equations from comparative literature to each other, as seen in Fig. 2 it is also evident that they do not always align perfectly. The differences in measurement procedure influence the result proving that new measurements are necessary when changing the reactor concept. The measurement can still give an idea of the change in reaction temperature at different system pressures and the pressure dependence of the different reaction systems can be visualised.

3.3. Dehydration at 50 mbar in five charging-discharging cycles

As explained in the previous Chapter 2.3 it is not only important to determine the influence of system pressure on the reaction temperature but also to see the effect on the cycle stability of the reaction system when lower pressure is applied during dehydration. Fig. 4 (a) shows the conversion of the dehydration reaction which was calculated according to Equation (3) while Fig. 4 (b) shows the temperature rise during the hydration for up to five runs for each system.

The dehydration heating profiles used and the maximum time the dehydration took to reach the maximum conversion for each system are given in Table 5. Fig. 4 shows good cycle stability in five cycles of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, H_3BO_3 and $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. No agglomeration formed during the dehydration and hydration reaction of all TCMs. Only foaming was a problem for the systems used in mineral oil, especially for

Table 7

Experimental values of enthalpy and entropy change during dehydration compared to other values from literature.

Dehydration step		Experimental	Comparison	Comparison
$\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CaCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\Delta_R H^\circ$	62.33	59.52 [50]	50.60 [56]
	$\Delta_R S^\circ$	139.25	132.80 [50]	114.00 [56]
$\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 \rightarrow \text{HBO}_2$	$\Delta_R H^\circ$	125.19	63.73 [52]	190.60 [51]
	$\Delta_R S^\circ$	298.13	150.01 [52]	442.98 [51]
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\Delta_R H^\circ$	121.04	111.69 [52]	111.73 [51]
	$\Delta_R S^\circ$	323.43	298.56 [52]	298.59 [51]
$\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{K}_2\text{CO}_3$	$\Delta_R H^\circ$	192.00	197.39 [52]	202.10 [51]
	$\Delta_R S^\circ$	455.37	467.46 [52]	470.94 [51]

Fig. 4. Conversion of the dehydration reaction (a) and temperature rise during hydration (b) over up to five runs for the different reaction systems.

Fig. 5. Influence of pressure and temperature on the dehydration of $K_2CO_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ in silicone oil – heating profiles (a) and conversion rates (b).

$CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$. The heating rate and solid content had to be reduced significantly (down to 10 wt% solid) to complete the five runs without the reactor overflowing. The temperature rise has been adjusted for a 30 wt% solid mixture to be comparable to the measurement points of the other systems shown in Fig. 4 (b). The H_3BO_3 system also showed some sublimation of the material which resublimated on parts of the reactor lid. This leads to the conclusion that reactive material was lost, but there was no visible effect in the measured conversion/temperature rise. The volatility of H_3BO_3 was previously observed by Huber et al. 2019 [58]. Overall, the results suggest a stable reaction in five cycles for all tested TCM. These cycles were conducted to determine the basic cyclability characteristics. Since seasonal storage requires stability over 20–40 cycles [59] these tests need to be extended, but the current results look promising.

3.4. Influence of system pressure and maximum temperature on the dehydration rate

While all four systems show potential, $K_2CO_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ and $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ were chosen for further investigation due to their low reaction temperature, which is interesting for the intended application, as well as their low corrosiveness and non-volatility. The results of the tests on the dehydration reaction rate demonstrate that both reducing the system pressure from 1013 mbar to 50 mbar and increasing the temperature from 140 °C to 175 °C significantly accelerate the dehydration rate of $K_2CO_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ under comparable heating conditions, shown in Fig. 5 (a). The corresponding conversion curves in Fig. 5 (b) indicate that, in both cases, the reaction time is reduced to one-third compared to dehydration at 140 °C and ambient pressure. Table 8 lists the maximum dehydration rates r_i as previously defined in Equation (4). Lowering the system pressure from ambient pressure to 50 mbar at 140 °C increases the maximum dehydration reaction rate by 1.5 for $K_2CO_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$, similar to an increased maximum temperature of 175 °C at ambient pressure, which increases the rate by 1.8.

Similar results were observed for $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, as lowering the system pressure to 50 mbar during dehydration at 120 °C also shortened the time to reach maximum conversion by a factor of three, as illustrated in Fig. 6. Additionally, as shown in Table 8, $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ is even more sensitive to changes in system pressure, as a pressure of 50 mbar results in a 2.1-fold increase in the dehydration reaction rate compared to

Table 8
Dehydration reaction rates at different operating conditions.

	p	T	r_i	factor
	mbar	°C	s^{-1}	–
$K_2CO_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$	1013	140	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.0
	50	140	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.5
	1013	175	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.8
$CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$	1013	120	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.0
	50	120	$8.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.1

ambient pressure at 120 °C. This corresponds to the Van't Hoff plots shown in Fig. 3 of Chapter 3.2, which also revealed a higher pressure dependence for the dehydration starting temperature of $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ in comparison to the other systems.

However, to avoid excessive foaming during $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ dehydration, the solid content had to be reduced to 10 wt%, enabling the use of higher heating rates. As reducing solid content lowers the energy density and increases the required reactor volume, future work should focus on developing foaming mitigation strategies to improve practical applicability.

3.5. Influence of system pressure and starting temperature on the hydration reaction

Hydrating K_2CO_3 and $CuSO_4 \cdot H_2O$ at higher relative pressures $p_{relative}$ of 0, 4, and 8 bar is expected to have minimal impact on reaction rate and temperature rise because the volume change with liquid water is significantly lower than during the dehydration with gaseous water [23]. The theoretical volume changes during hydration are –7.5 % for the K_2CO_3 hydrates and

–14.9 % for the $CuSO_4$ hydrates, compared to substantial increases of + 55860 % for the K_2CO_3 hydrates and + 110310 % for the $CuSO_4$ hydrates during dehydration. Any pressure effect on hydration is likely to be slightly positive. Table 9 provides the densities and molar masses of the hydrates used for these calculations.

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 visualise the results of the experiments in the high-pressure steel reactor. The measured temperature rise $\Delta T_{measured}$ is given in Fig. 7 (a) and Fig. 8 (a) (full columns) as well as the corrected temperature rise $\Delta T_{corrected}$ (striped columns), which is calculated using the mixing temperature $T_{mix,0}$ and Equations (10) and (11). As previously explained, this correction is necessary since preheating the water is not feasible in the setup. Fig. 7 (b) and Fig. 8 (b) show the time until the maximum temperature T_{max} is reached ($t(T_{max})$). A detailed overview of these values is given in the APPENDIX in Table A1 and Table A2.

The corrected values in Fig. 7 (a) suggest that there is no significant influence on the temperature rise at varied pressures and temperatures for the K_2CO_3 system. Pressure does not seem to influence the temperature rise for the $CuSO_4$ either, but the corrected temperature rise increases at higher temperatures as Fig. 8 (a) shows.

Temperature rise: For both systems, the measured temperature rise seen in Fig. 8 decreases at higher starting temperatures due to increased heat losses to the environment and the greater temperature difference between the suspension and the added cold water. These losses to the environment are not accounted for in the corrected values, but the significantly lower water temperatures (17–20 °C) are. The correction accounts for the cooling effect of the added water by incorporating a mixing temperature as seen in Equation (9) to determine the actual starting temperature.

The maximum achievable reaction enthalpy increases with temperature. However, since the reaction is exothermic, higher temperatures

Fig. 6. Influence of pressure and temperature on the dehydration of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in mineral oil – heating profiles (a) and conversion rates (b).

Table 9

Properties of the investigated hydrates of K_2CO_3 and CuSO_4 and water [51,52,60].

	Density	Molar mass
	g/cm^3	g/mol
$\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2043	165.24
K_2CO_3	2290	138.21
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2286	249.68
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	3168	177.62
$\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(l)}$	997	18.02
$\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$	0.598	18.02

also reduce the expected conversion to products. These opposing effects result in the corrected temperature rise remaining nearly constant for the K_2CO_3 system across different starting temperatures. In contrast, the corrected temperature rise of the CuSO_4 system increases with higher starting temperatures. This suggests a stronger temperature dependence of the CuSO_4 reaction, which aligns with the thermodynamic data from *HSC Chemistry 6.1* [51], which contains the temperature dependence of

enthalpy of formation in its dataset, based on empirical Shomate equations.

Reaction rate: The reaction time or the time until the maximum temperature is reached at different pressures and temperatures is shown in Fig. 7 (b) and Fig. 8 (b). It is not entirely clear from the results whether temperature or pressure influences the reaction time. For the K_2CO_3 system, the reaction seems to be faster the higher the pressure is at 25 °C and 50 °C, but at 75 °C suspension temperature, this effect is not visible. This either means that the negative effect of temperature on the reaction equilibrium outweighs it, or that the measurement is no longer accurate enough, which is highly likely as the measured temperature rise is only 2 °C and the resolution of the temperature measurement is only full degrees. For the CuSO_4 system, the reaction appears to be slightly slower at higher pressures, but only at 25 °C and 50 °C, at 75 °C, no effect is detected. The most likely explanation for these opposing results is that the measurement of this value is not accurate enough. The only clear conclusion that can be drawn is that the hydration of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ reaches the maximum temperature faster than the hydration of K_2CO_3 (~124 s compared to ~ 211 s).

Fig. 7. Influence of pressure and suspension start temperature on the hydration of K_2CO_3 – temperature rise (a) and time until the maximum temperature is reached (b).

Fig. 8. Influence of pressure and suspension start temperature on the hydration of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ – temperature rise (a) and time until the maximum temperature is reached (b).

Experiments at higher temperatures: The current setup at higher pressure has limitations such as thermal losses, a small suspension volume relative to the reactor volume, and no preheating of the water, which prevents detecting a temperature rise at starting temperatures over 100 °C for K_2CO_3 , and even for $CuSO_4 \cdot H_2O$, the losses were too great. Therefore, the effects of pressure on temperature rise and reaction time were studied at lower temperatures (up to 75 °C), where these issues are less pronounced. Still, it can be stated that no agglomeration occurred up to 130 °C for K_2CO_3 , so further experiments in an improved setup should be conducted.

Experiments with $CuSO_4 \cdot H_2O$ showed no agglomeration up to 105 °C either, but agglomeration occurred at ≥ 110 °C under 4 and 8 bar, likely due to hydrate melting. While higher pressure can delay dehydration by shifting the equilibrium, it has little effect on melting. Literature reports melting and/or decomposition of $CuSO_4 \cdot H_2O$ at ~ 110 °C [61,62]. Palacios et al. 2023 [59] Also measured a melting point of 111 °C and stated that salt hydrates may melt before decomposing, especially under fast heating, like Mamani et al. 2018 [63] reported. This suggests $CuSO_4 \cdot H_2O$ could melt above 110 °C if decomposition is suppressed by pressure. Thus, efficient hydration above 110 °C is uncertain and needs further study, but the system appears promising below 110 °C.

4. Conclusion

This work investigated the influence of system pressure on the dehydration and hydration of $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, H_3BO_3 , $K_2CO_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ and $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ in a three-phase suspension reactor. The reactor type was chosen due to its enhanced heat transfer, good scalability and ability to prevent particle agglomeration without introducing a host matrix. The aim was to help close a gap in the literature regarding the pressure sensitivity of salt hydrate reactions in a reactor configuration not commonly studied for TCES.

Lowering the system pressure in the reactor during charging significantly reduced the dehydration onset temperature by 33–66 °C (see Fig. 2) and increased the dehydration rate by up to 2.1 times (for $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ see Table 8). Stable cycling behaviour was observed for all materials over five dehydration–hydration cycles (Fig. 4), with no

Appendix

Tables A1 and A2 show the obtained temperature rise $\Delta T_{measured}$, the time until the maximum temperature T_{max} is reached $t(T_{max})$ as well as the calculated mixing temperature $T_{mix,0}$ and corrected temperature rise $\Delta T_{corrected}$ from the hydration experiments at higher system pressures.

Table A1

Influence of pressure and starting temperature on the hydration of K_2CO_3 .

Prelative	T_0	T_{water}	$T_{mix,0}$	T_{max}	$\Delta T_{measured}$	$\Delta T_{corrected}$	$t(T_{max})$
bar	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C	s
0	25	18	24	36	11	12	215
4	25	18	24	36	11	12	208
8	25	18	24	34	9	10	146
0	50	19	44	58	8	14	244
4	50	19	44	57	7	13	192
8	50	19	44	58	8	14	163
0	75	17	64	77	2	13	265
4	75	17	64	77	2	13	202
8	75	17	64	77	2	13	269

agglomeration. Meanwhile, hydration tests using liquid water at system pressures of up to 8 bar confirmed the feasibility of rapid hydration, even at temperatures of up to 75 °C. The hydration reaction rate remained largely pressure-independent (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8).

Overall, the findings demonstrate that system pressure control can enhance operational flexibility, broaden the fields of application of the storage system, and will be valuable for scale-up of the technology.

Future work should extend the cycle stability tests to 20–40 cycles to confirm long-term stability for seasonal heat storage, explore pressurised hydration at temperatures > 110 °C, especially for $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ and assess these effects for other suitable solid–gas reactions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lena Schmieder: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Sandra Jezernik:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Simon Gatt:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Noah Steinacher:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Franz Winter:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Table A2

Influence of pressure and starting temperature on the hydration of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Prelative	T_0	T_{water}	$T_{\text{mix},0}$	T_{max}	$\Delta T_{\text{measured}}$	$\Delta T_{\text{corrected}}$	$t(T_{\text{max}})$
bar	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C	s
0	25	20	23	36	20	12	118
4	25	20	23	36	20	12	122
8	25	20	23	34	22	10	172
0	50	20	41	58	18	14	112
4	50	20	41	57	17	13	104
8	50	20	41	58	18	14	140
0	75	20	59	77	16	13	119
4	75	20	59	77	15	13	114
8	75	20	59	77	15	13	119

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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